

POSSIBILITIES OF THE PLASTIC INDUSTRY IN INDIA.*

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India with her vast natural resources and splendid man-power occupies a rather insignificant position industrially even now. Particularly appalling is the situation with respect to the plastic industry whose rise has justly resulted in the present age being called as the plastic age. Last year a feature of more than ordinary interest was the opening of "Plasti-City" a plastic exhibit, in Washington, sponsored jointly by the Chemical Division of the Department of Commerce in America and the staff of the famous magazine—the Modern Plastics. Every phase of American life from household appliances to national defence preparations was represented in the exhibition. Clothes made from plastics, interior designs and decorations for architectural purposes, plastic applications in the aeronautic and automobiles as well as a whole variety of sporting goods and accessories, raw materials, moulding powder, rods, tubes, sheets and pre-forms were the special features of the show which established beyond doubt the great future of this new and interesting industry.

Just as the dyestuffs industry deals with naturally occurring dyestuffs and synthetic dyes, so can this industry be divided into two parts, namely, naturally occurring resins and synthetic resins. Although the present usage has developed mostly in the form of synthetic resins, as uniformity of product is guaranteed in the synthetic field, there is no doubt that more and more attention will be paid to naturally occurring resins owing to the varying types of uses to which these resins can be put when modified by suitable chemical and physical processes.

Amongst the synthetic resins may be mentioned the following :—

A. CONDENSATION POLYMERS :

1. Resinox, bakelite, durer.
2. Beetle or plaskon.
3. Melamine resin.
4. Nylon.
5. Beckosol, glyptal, duraplex.
6. Amberol, becacite maleic resins.
7. Paraplex.
8. Thiokol.

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B. LINEAR POLYMERS :

1. Styron.
2. Cumar, picco, nevindine.
3. Vistanex.
4. Acryloid.
5. Lucite, crystallite.
6. Gelva, vinylite A.
7. Polyvinyl alcohol.
8. Butvar, butacite, vinylite X YSG.
9. Koroseal.
10. Saran.
11. Neoprene.
12. Buna SS.

C. CO-POLYMERS :

1. Vinylite V
2. Acryloid.
3. Buna S.
4. Perbunan.

1. Resinox, bakelite and durez are prepared by the condensation of phenol and its homologue with formaldehyde, the former being obtained by the interaction of benzene with chlorine and the hydrolysis of chlorobenzene to produce phenol.

2. Beetle or plaskon types of resins are obtained by suitably reacting carbon dioxide gas and ammonia gas to form urea which in turn is condensed with formaldehyde.

3. When nitrogen is passed over calcium carbide under suitable conditions, calcium cyanamide is obtained, and from this compound, cyanamide and melamine are produced. The latter is used as a raw material for several types of melamine resins, such as shellac-melamine resins and those formed by condensation with formaldehyde.

4. The raw material necessary for the production of nylon, which has found the most recent application in the textile industry and which might replace the very popular natural silk fibre, is phenol. Various types of nylons can be obtained depending on the type of acid obtained or employed during the reaction, such as adipic, sebacic acid etc.

5. Naphthalene is the starting material for the production of resins such as glyptal, beckosol and duraplex. When naphthalene is oxidised by air, it forms phthalic anhydride. This anhydride when interacted with a mixture of glycerine and linoleic acid forms the type of resins mentioned above.

From the above list of the more important resins, one can easily infer what raw materials must be made available in India before the plastic industry can be introduced in this country.

Of these raw materials, perhaps the most important ones are phenol and formaldehyde. Phenols and cresylic acids are produced in reasonable quantities by the Bararee Coke Works and the Shalimar Tar Products. The plant for the manufacture of toluene, set up by the Tatas, ought to result in the further increase of available phenolic by-products, but these industries must be developed still further to enable India to produce sufficient phenolic substances. Formaldehyde can be produced from methyl alcohol in the dry distillation of wood or it can be synthesised from alcohol. As both methyl and ethyl alcohols are available in this country, there should be no difficulty in producing the necessary formaldehyde. As a result of the impetus given by the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research and Dr. H. K. Sen of the Lac Research Institute, a couple of pilot plants is already manufacturing some formaldehyde. It is quite easy to multiply these plants which can be constructed locally. Amongst other aldehydes, which can be conveniently developed in this country for resin manufacture, may be mentioned furfural. We have obtained good yields of it from rice husk, but there are many other types of cheap cellulosic materials available in India such as water-hyacinth, jute waste etc., and it is quite feasible to manufacture furfural cheaply in this country from any one of these sources.

From the point of view of the plastic industry perhaps the next in order of importance are those resins which depend on urea, calcium carbide and acetylene as the starting materials. For example melamine (see 3) and vinyl resins (see 14 and 17) need calcium carbide and acetylene respectively. The manufacture of calcium carbide industry in this country is an important event. It is gratifying to note that pilot plant work in this connection has been completed and my friend Dr. J. C. Ghosh feels that it is quite feasible for him to make a ton a day of this material in Bangalore itself. Acetylene is an important material not only for the resins but for all metal and engineering industries and we hope that the Government and the public will see to an early establishment of this industry in India. Cheap and abundant supplies of power are the main requisites of this industry. Nylon, the fascinating new resin, can be easily developed as both adipic and sebacic acid can be readily manufactured in this country. The only materials which will have to be developed on the large scale are phenolic products. We are already doing laboratory work on the production of nylon. The cracking process in petroleum industries, now

employed both in Assam and Rawalpindi, can provide starting materials for the development of styrene and synthetic rubber products and will no doubt engage the early attention of oil companies.

Carbon dioxide and ammonia form a set of raw materials for the manufacture of urea-formaldehyde resins such as beetle and plaskon. Carbon dioxide is readily and plentifully available in India. Ammonia, required in the production of urea, is manufactured at present in limited quantities by Messrs. Mysore Chemicals & Fertilizers Ltd. and Messrs. Tata Chemicals Ltd. and it is not unlikely that these firms will be able to meet the demands made by the plastic industry, if required. Ample supplies of glycerine are available in India and the principal firms manufacturing it as a bye-product in the soap industry are Messrs. Tata Oil Mills, Messrs. Lever Bros. and Messrs. Swaika Oil Mills, Lillooha.

It is not for war purposes only that synthetic plastic materials are required in India. It is obvious that a country with such large supplies of vegetable and cracked oil gases, glycerine and cellulosic matter must be deeply interested in the plastic products. The great Jute Industry of Bengal and the growing Textile Industry with its cotton waste and the short-staple cotton and other fibre cultivators urgently feel the need of this industry as without this their bye-products and wastes cannot be suitably developed. The boards, the corrugated sheets and the containers, which can be made from moulding powders, contain fifty or more percentage of this material and fifty per cent of one of these synthetic resins.

In the absence of the synthetic resins Indian workers have addressed themselves to the problem of utilising naturally occurring resin sources for various purposes and it would not be out of place to mention some of the resins which have been successfully developed already. They are as follows:—

1. Lac.
2. Casein.
3. Resins from bagasse and jute waste.
4. Resins from coffee beans
5. Resins from oils.
6. Resins from oil-seed cakes.
7. Resins from horn waste.
8. Resins from *Sarcostemma Brevistigma*.

LAC RESINS.

Amongst the naturally occurring resins perhaps lac occupies one of the most important positions. It has been used from times immemorial

but lac as such suffers from several defects which can be cured by chemical and physical treatment. One of the first most important applications which stimulated its export considerably was in the manufacture of gramophone records, which developed during the closing decades of the last century. Since then the export trade has been steadily on the increase. This may be regarded as a direct result of the scientific and industrial research pursued by a number of agencies interested directly in lac production and its consumption.

The first serious programme of research work in this line was laid down by the Indian Lac Research Institute, Namkum which included agricultural, entomological, chemical and physical problems. The U. S. Shellac Importers Association sponsored the New York Shellac Research Bureau which was chiefly concerned with problems of the consumers and those dealing with standardization of the product. Shellac users in Great Britain felt a similar necessity and managed to induce the Indian Lac Research Institute to finance and bring into being the London Shellac Research Bureau, which has produced some of the most important and far-reaching results both in pure and applied fields of lac research. Lastly, the efforts of the laboratories of the Director of Scientific and Industrial Research may be mentioned, which emphasised the development of lac consuming industries in India, a function which had generally taken second place as compared with the activities calculated to assist and encourage the consumers of lac abroad.

In the following paragraphs a brief resume of the results of these researches is presented with a view to indicate how intensive research can help to develop new uses for an age old product like lac and keep its demand alive inspite of the keen competition presented by a flood of synthetic resins now on the market.

One of the early pieces of work done at the Indian Lac Research Institute concerns the use of accelerators in conjunction with lac, which may be looked upon as catalytic agents for promoting the condensation and polymerizing reactions in the resin mass. Thus, small quantities of substance such as urea, thiourea, aluminium chloride, oxalic acid, tetrachlorophthalic acid, phthalic anhydride, sulphanilic acid, dicyanidamine, etc. etc., when added to a lac composition considerably reduce the polymerizing time and improve the product. These researches of Aldis have been made the basis of moulding powders prepared at the New York Shellac Research Bureau and of electric bulb capping cement for use in high speed automatic production. The results of this work have proved useful in a number of other industries as well, where lac need be hardened.

One of very first pieces of work of the London Shellac Research Bureau involved the recognition of the superior -properties of hard resin component of lac and the development of new methods for fractionating lac applicable to commercial scale operations. This line of research attracted active attention of other workers in India, America, Germany and other countries, with the result that there now exist at least five distinctly different processes, some of which are being commercially exploited in Germany and Great Britain. The main features of hard lac resin which have made it industrially important include its ease of hardening, higher softening point, low solvent retentivity, capacity to produce hard, flexible and extremely adhesive films, high temperature resistance, freedom from greening of copper when applied as an electrical insulation, low water-sensitivity, etc. The list of its virtues appears to be almost too good to be true, but carefully prepared material has shown all these advantages to exist, and the improvement over original whole lac is definitely marked. As a result of these properties the hard lac resin has found application in numerous industries where quality rather than cost is the chief criterion, for instance as electrical insulation, as tin and aluminium foil lacquers, and others.

Sulphited lac composition developed by the same workers consists of a combination of lac with sulphite through oxonium linkages. It is produced by reaction with alkali bisulphites and sulphites as well as sulphurous acid. The process is unique in as much as it makes possible the deposition of the solid resinous content of a solution in a polymerized insoluble form merely by virtue of evaporation of the solvent. Furthermore, the solution exhibits strong emulsifying power towards oils and fats. Thus the possibilities of its application cover a large field such as water-proof water paints and distempers with or without emulsified drying oils, emulsion-varnishes in water medium for stoving and baking enamels, plastic mouldings, polishes for producing hardened and water-proof films on wood, plaster and metal surfaces, finishes for petrol tanks and containers, sizing materials and polishes with emulsified wax, etc.

Production of oil-lac varnishes, which had been attempted by numerous workers cannot be said to have been successfully accomplished until the London Shellac Research Bureau developed the indirect method of solubilising lac in oil by first dissolving it in fatty acids and then esterifying the solution to produce mixed esters of lac and fatty acids. In this connection one must mention previous attempts of dissolving lac in drying oils at high temperatures through the use of red lead and other agents. Both the processes proved their usefulness, for instance the laboratories of the Director, Scientific and Industrial Research recently opened up two big

fields for its use in anti-gas cloth and in treatment of wood. As a result of these latter developments shellac has found a large market in this country which is bound to expand in the future.

In order to improve film forming properties of spirit varnishes made from lac, it had long been felt that suitable plasticisers must be discovered. First comprehensive study of this problem was made by the New York Shellac Research Bureau, while a more systematic evaluation of various available plasticisers was carried out by the London Shellac Research Bureau and some work was also done at the Indian Lac Research Institute. As a result of these studies certain materials such as sextol, phthalate, *cyclohexanol tartrate*, *p*-toluene sulphonamide and certain others, described by trade names, have been found to be effective. These plasticisers not only impart plastic properties to lac films, *viz.*, flexibility and resistance against creasing, but also retain or improve such useful properties as are already possessed by ordinary lac films, for instance, water resistance, mechanical strength, adhesiveness, resistance against blushing etc. Consequently the range of application of shellac varnishes is appreciably increased and the quality of products improved, exemplified by such industries as wood polishing, metal finishing, spirit paints, metal foil printing, treatment of textile fabrics, etc.

While dealing with the subject of spirit varnishes, it may be of interest to point out in passing that due to the acidic nature of lac, its spirit solutions have the disadvantage of darkening when stored in metallic containers. To prevent this discolouration, minute quantity of oxalic acid is added which not only prevents the development of dark colour, but actually reduces the colour of varnish by a mere shade. The mechanism of this reaction was studied electrometrically at the London Shellac Research Bureau.

Comparatively recent work of Gidvani and Bhattacharya on the production of esters, ethers and ether-esters of shellac deserves more than a passing mention, for the possibilities of industrial application of these products cover a large industrial field, which include plasticisers, paints and varnishes, linoleum, leather finishes and polishes, rubber like goods, insulating materials, textile impregnants for parachute and anti-gas fabrics, packing and jointing materials, specially elastic paints for rubber surfaces etc.

Another interesting material that has been developed by the London Shellac Research Bureau is the fibrous lac which is obtained in two different forms by the action of formaldehyde on either ammoniacal or on bisulphite solution of lac. The structure of this product indicates the formation of a linear chain molecule which may lead to interesting applications in the

form of extrusion products and spun materials. Used as a basis for varnish manufacture, it yields water resistant and quick drying films.

Combinations of cellulose lacquers with shellac and shellac products have formed a subject of research at different times at all the three lac research organisations at Namkum, New York and London as a result of which considerable data have accumulated which are valuable to the cellulose lacquer industry in assisting it to produce harder, glossier, better weather resistant and more economical lacquers for the trade.

Hot spraying of powdered lac either neat or mixed with addition agents may be regarded as an important industrial development carried out at London. This technique does away with the use of solvent as a vehicle and enables fine films of lac to be deposited on metal, wood, fabric or other surfaces. The troubles arising from the solvent retention nature of lac films, such as water sensitivity etc. are thus automatically eliminated. Possible application of this process includes a whole series of industries where shellac films are applied as protective or decorative coatings, exemplified by laminated products, french polishing, anti-fouling coatings for ship's bottoms, oil storage tanks etc.

So far, one of the chief drawbacks of moulding powders based on shellac had been their inadequacy for use in moulding equipment employed by thermo-setting type of materials such as the phenolics. The latter have a much shorter curing period and the rate of production consequently is high. The newly developed shellac-urea-formaldehyde powders produced by the Indian Lac Research Institute approach very closely the phenolics in this respect and possess other useful characteristics, which make them valuable for industrial exploitation particularly under present day war time conditions.

Other developments of Indian Lac Research Institute include the colourless adhesives made from aleuritic acid, suitable for use in safety glass, shellac-coal tar combinations for the production of moulding powders, plasticine like masses, adhesives and baking enamels, utilisation of destructive distillation products obtained from Kiri for the manufacture of stoving lacquers, shellac-casein moulding powders etc.

Investigations on solvents and solutions of lac at the Indian Lac Research Institute are worthy of note not only from scientific but also industrial point of view. These studies reveal among other things how small quantities of impurities present in solvents improve their solvent power, and how combinations of two non-solvents may constitute a good solvent for lac.

As mentioned earlier, the activities of the laboratories of the Director of Scientific and Industrial Research in relation to lac have been concentrated on the industrial utilization of lac in this country. Towards this goal a number of products have been developed which have made possible the initiation of new industries in India. These include the manufacture of anti-gas cloth, the laminated paper board, the corrugated jute board etc. Other lines of work which are now under way include the resin impregnation of wood, treatment of jute mill bobbins, production of water-proof plywood, all of which have developed far enough to indicate possibilities of commercialization in the very near future.

COFFEE-BEAN PLASTICS.

Before the outbreak of war, India was exporting a large amount of raw coffee to other countries, but on account of the export restriction arising as a result of the outbreak of war the "Coffee Planters Association of India" felt the necessity of finding out some other suitable outlet for their surplus coffee. Perhaps it is well known that coffee beans have been dumped into the sea in Brazil and South America owing to over-production. It was, therefore, suggested to us to undertake an investigation into the possibilities of the utilization of raw coffee for the preparation of moulding powders.

After a year of systematic investigation we have been successful in developing a process for the production of a moulding powder from coffee beans. The outlines of the manufacturing process are as follows:—

The green coffee beans are dried in an oven to facilitate their grinding. Dirt and stones are eliminated by a common flotation process. Broken beans, black beans, sticks or any cellulosic material do not necessarily have to be removed. The powdered coffee beans are made oil-free by refluxing with a suitable solvent. The oil-free powder is subjected to digestion at a fairly high steam pressure with a suitable chemical and in presence of fairly large quantities of water for a certain definite interval of time. The resultant material is washed and ground to a suitable fineness. This powder after mixing with a suitable plasticiser is ready for moulding purposes.

The articles prepared from the above powder are very strong, offer a good resistance to water, take a nice finish and can be drilled, sawed and machined. The flow of coffee bean resins is not quite as good as that of the bakelite type of resins, but investigations show that it can be improved.

This non-beverage use of the surplus and even the poorest quality coffee may provide a new industry.

The bye-products of coffee plastic manufacture are also of interest. Coffee-oil, for instance, is a bye-product which can find many important uses. It is rich in vitamin-D and hence should find use in cosmetics, lotions, medicines and fine quality soaps. It can be used as paint oil or cooking oil. And of course, coffee is a plain source of caffeine valuable in medicine and pharmaceutical fields.

OIL-SEED PLASTICS.

Oil seed cakes due to their limited demand as cattle food and organic manure and their bad keeping qualities in tropical climate, but particularly due to the recent export difficulties, drew attention as a subject for the Plastic Industry.

Earlier experiments consisted in the extraction of proteins from the oil cakes by dissolving the former in dilute alkalis and later precipitating with dilute acids. These proteins after hardening by treatment with certain aldehydes, were mixed with suitable fillers, plasticisers, water-proofing agents and finally moulded at definite pressure and temperature.

In another set of experiments the mass left after the protein extraction along with certain basic compounds, was hydrolysed at a fairly high pressure. The product obtained was treated with certain naturally occurring aldehydes and chemicals and later moulded under specific condition of temperature and pressure.

It was observed that mouldings from the second type of experiments were stronger and more water resistant than in the first case. They fairly compare with phenol-formaline products.

RESIN FROM *Sarcostemma Brevistigma*.

The different names ascribed to the *Sarcostemma Brevistigma* are:— Sanskrit and Bombay—Soma ; Hindi and Bengali—Somalata ; Marhatta—Kondopata and in Telgu—Mawa Kiriya. It is also called the Moonplant. It has been described (Dictionary of the Economic Products of India by Watt Vol. VI, pt. II, pp. 477) as a trailing leafless, jointed shrub, not uncommonly met with in dry rocky places in the Deccan Peninsula. It occurs also in Bengal, but more rarely than on the western side of India. Dr. Gibson mentions that "it is often brought from a distance by farmers to extirpate white ants from the sugar fields. A bundle of twigs is put into the trough of the well from which the field is watered along with a bag of salt, hard packed, so that it may dissolve gradually. The water so impregnated destroys the ants without injuring the crop." The plant

contains a large amount of milky sap, which Roxburgh says "is of a mild nature and acid taste, and is often used by Native travellers to allay their thirst. It has been used also in preparing an intoxicating liquor."

It has been possible to prepare a resin from this material by suitable treatment. The softening point of the resin is 60-65°C. The resin, so obtained, is soluble in benzene but not in other common solvents. The resin is capable of yielding a good moulding powder with saw dust and wood powder. Although insoluble in water, it is not so resistant to water action as to compete with other synthetic resins with respect to this quality. By suitable chemical treatments, however, it is possible to improve this property of the resin.

RESINS FROM BAGASSE AND JUTE WASTE.

Cellulosic matter and lignin of which enormous amounts are annually thrown away as a waste product in our sugar mills have drawn the attention of various workers as a source of cheap plastic material. A patent has recently been taken by the Government in which after a thorough and careful investigation of the working conditions, it has been shown that as much as 19% resin can be obtained out of bagasse with little chemical treatment. The broad outlines of the process are given below:

The bagasse from a sugar mill is washed well with water and dried in the open sun. When it is dry, it is powdered either in a grinder or preferably a defibrator to the required mesh. The powdered bagasse is then subjected to steam hydrolysis under pressure in an autoclave. The ratio of water to bagasse, duration of hydrolysis and the temperature and pressure conditions have to be carefully watched and regulated to effect the maximum conversion of the ligno-cellulosic matter into resinous matter. The resin, thus formed within the fibrous cells of bagasse, is extracted by boiling the dry hydrolysed stuff with spirit or alcohol for the pre-determined period. The resin being soluble in spirit is extracted out of the fibrous tissue during the process of refluxing. An alcoholic resinous extract is thus obtained. It has an excess of the solvent and to get rid of it, the alcohol is distilled off. The thick resinous mass is left behind in the retort. Even without alcoholic extraction it is possible to use the fibrous powder as such, as a moulding powder. Should it be necessary to obtain the resin in a powdered form, the last traces of the solvent can be removed over a water-bath. The resin is a dark brown, lustrous mass brittle in nature. It has good binding and water-proofing properties. The melting point varies over a wide range but a fairly average value is

about 148°C. It can be plasticised in the usual manner. Recent investigations show that if the bagasse is hydrolysed in an alkaline or acidic medium, the yield is improved by 2 to 3% with no substantial change in the properties of the resin.

I hope and trust that this survey of some of the important naturally occurring resins and the intensely fascinating synthetic resins will stimulate our Fellows and result in the future expansion of scientific investigations in every direction of this interesting field resulting in the early development of a plastic industry in India worthy of her great natural resources.

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